

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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APPENDIX A: TABLES

Table A. Antecedents of Triple-A SC capabilities in previous research

Triple-A SC paper	Antecedents	Consequences	Theory	Findings
Dubey et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SC visibility • Information-sharing • SC connectivity • Top management commitment (moderator variable) 	---	Resource-based view (RBV)	Information-sharing and SC connectivity resources influence SC visibility capability, which, under the moderating effect of top management commitment, enhances all AAA capabilities.
Aslam et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial orientation • SC learning orientation (related to alignment in the article) 	---	Dynamic capabilities view (DCV)	The weaker direct effects of entrepreneurial orientation compared to the indirect effects indicate that an SC learning orientation mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and dynamic SC capabilities (SC agility, SC adaptability, market sensing).
Srimarut and Mekhum (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SC connectivity • Big data analytics capability 	--	RBV	SC connectivity plays a significant positive role in building the firm’s big data analytics capability. Big data analytics significantly positively influences AAA capabilities.
Yang (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge management capability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational performance • Relational performance 	Knowledge management (KM) capabilities	Knowledge management capabilities are conducive to the development of AAA capabilities, which in turn lead to the improvement of relational and operational performance.
Ahmed (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lean strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Firm competitive capability 	Resource orchestration theory (ROT)	Lean strategy finds it difficult to create adaptability. Firms that adopt agile strategies are more adaptable than those that adopt lean strategies and can strategically align their resources to build CA.
Ahmed and Rashidi (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lean strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust SC • Resilient SC 	ROT	Lean strategy finds it challenging to create adaptability. Lean strategy, adaptability, and agility are not related to resilient SC. Adaptability is not related to robust SC.
Garrido-Vega et al. (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive environment (competitive intensity and SC complexity) • Business strategy (cost versus differentiation) 	---	Dynamic capabilities view (DCV) Contingency theory (CT)	Competitive environment and business strategy are positively related to AAA capabilities, except for SC complexity, which does not seem to affect agility. Although the competitive environment variables affect the business strategy, the latter has no mediating effects between the competitive environment and SC agility, adaptability, and alignment capabilities

Khan et al. (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SC data analytics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-covid disruption performance 	DCV	<p>SC data analytics contributes positively and significantly to agility and adaptability (but not to alignment) and all AAA capabilities positively impact post-covid disruption performance.</p> <p>The connection between SC data analytics and disruption performance is significantly influenced through all AAA capabilities.</p>
Huma and Ahmed (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visibility • Flexibility • Velocity 	----	RBV	<p>Direct significant relationship between visibility and adaptability.</p> <p>Mediating effect of agility on visibility and adaptability, and velocity and alignment.</p> <p>The relationship of flexibility with SC-AAA capabilities is positively significant. Visibility relationships with agility and alignment are positively significant. Velocity relationships with agility and adaptability are also positively significant</p>
Iranmanesh et al. (2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational SC Transparency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intention to adopt Blockchain 	RBV CT	<p>SC transparency leads directly to SC alignment and adaptability and indirectly causes SC agility. The influence of SC transparency and agility on the intention to adopt blockchain is confirmed. Market turbulence positively moderates the link between agility and the intention to adopt blockchain.</p>
Tickle et al. (2024)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fourth-party logistics (4PL) adoption 	---	--	<p>4PL positively affects the AAA capabilities of Humanitarian SCs.</p> <p>AAA antecedent realignment, positioning alignment as a precursor to agility and adaptability.</p> <p>It identifies three core antecedents in Humanitarian SCs: flexibility, speed and environmental uncertainty.</p>

Table B. Construct and items of the scales

AA_FilterDevelop	Filter development countries (1), emerging (0)
LogPlantSize	COMPUTE LogPlantSize=LG10(PlantSize)
industry1elec	Electronic
industry2mach	Machinery
industry3auto	Automotive
AAA CAPABILITIES	Source: Marin-Garcia et al. (2018)
SC Adaptability	<i>Respondent: SC management</i>
Adapt11	Our production system is designed to accommodate changes in demand volume.
Adapt12	Our production system is designed to accommodate changes in production mix.
Adapt21	We have a good understanding of where our production technology stands, in terms of technology life cycles
Adapt22	Our plant stays on the leading edge of new technology in our industry.
Adapt31	In order to find potential new markets, we monitor economies around the world.
Adapt32	We are concerned about the needs of both our immediate customers and our ultimate consumers.
SC Agility	<i>Respondent: SC management</i>
Agil11	Supply chain applications with internal application within our organization (such as enterprise resource planning).
Agil12	Customer relationship applications with internal applications in our company.
Agil22	Our company strives to shorten supplier lead time, in order to avoid inventory and stockouts.
Agil23	Flexibility in response to requests for changes is a characteristic of our relationship with our key suppliers.
Agil31	We can add product variety without sacrificing quality.
Agil32	We can easily add significant product variety without increasing cost.
Agil33	Our capability for responding quickly to customization requirements is very high.
SC Alignment	<i>Respondent: SC management</i>
Align11	Our top managers repeatedly tell us that sharing supply chain risks and rewards with our customers is critical to our plant's success.
Align13	Our supply chain members have clearly defined goals within our supply chain.
Align22	We emphasize openness of communication in collaborating with our suppliers.
Align24	We should use unambiguous language and communication with our supply chain partners.
Align32	Cooperating with our suppliers is beneficial to us.
Align33	To what extent would you agree that Our supply chain partners understand our manufacturing capabilities
AMO MODEL	Source: Marin-Garcia and Martinez Tomas (2016)
Ability	
Task-related Training for Employees	<i>Respondent: Human Resource Management</i>
ETRAINN01	Our plant employees receive training and development in workplace skills, on a regular basis.
ETRAINN02	Management at this plant believes that continual training and upgrading of employee skills is important.
ETRAINN04	Our employees regularly receive training to improve their skills.
Multi-Function Employees	<i>Respondent: Human Resource Management</i>
MLTFNN01	Our employees receive training to perform multiple tasks.
MLTFNN02	Employees at this plant learn how to perform a variety of tasks.
MLTFNN04	Employees are cross-trained at this plant, so that they can fill in for others, if necessary.
Motivation	
Goal-Based Incentives	<i>Respondent: Human Resource Management</i>
INCTVN01	Our incentive system encourages us to vigorously pursue plant objectives.
INCTVN02	The incentive system at this plant encourages us to reach plant goals.
INCTVN03	Our incentive system is consistent with our plant goals. (Our incentive system is at odds with our plant goals).
Employee Suggestions Implementation and Feedback	<i>Respondent: Plant supervision</i>
ESUGGN01	Management takes all product and process improvement suggestions seriously.
ESUGGN02	We are encouraged to make suggestions for improving performance at this plant.

ESUGGN03	Management tells us why our suggestions are implemented or not used.
ESUGGN04	Many useful suggestions are implemented at this plant.
Opportunity	
<i>Small Group Problem Solving</i>	<i>Respondent: Plant supervision</i>
TEAMSN02	Our plant forms teams to solve problems.
TEAMSN03	In the past three years, many problems have been solved through small group sessions.
TEAMSN04	Problem solving teams have helped improve manufacturing processes at this plant.
<i>Decentralization of Authority</i>	<i>Respondent: Direct labor</i>
rCNATHN02	Reversed. A person who wants to make his own decisions would be quickly discouraged.
rCNATHN03	Reversed. Even small matters have to be referred to someone higher up for a final answer.
rCNATHN04	Reversed. I have to ask my boss before I do almost anything.
TOP MANAGEMENT SUPPORT	Source: Min et al. (2007)
<i>SCO-TMS (customers)</i>	<i>Respondent: SC management</i>
TOPCSN01	Relationships with our customers are considered to be of critical importance to our plant's top managers.
TOPCSN04	Our top managers support us in resolving conflicts with our customers, when they occur.
<i>SCO-TMS (suppliers)</i>	<i>Respondent: SC management</i>
TOPSPN01	Relationships with our suppliers are considered to be of critical importance to our plant's top managers.
TOPSPN04	Our top managers support us in resolving conflicts with our suppliers, when they occur.

Table C. Psychometric properties of lower order reflective composites

Lower Order Constructs	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Total sample				
ESUGGN	0.74	0.75	0.84	0.57
ETRAINN	0.79	0.79	0.88	0.70
INCTVN	0.88	0.88	0.92	0.80
MLTFNN	0.67	0.69	0.82	0.61
rCNATHN	0.85	0.85	0.91	0.77
TEAMSN	0.77	0.78	0.87	0.69
TOPCSN	0.67	0.67	0.82	0.60
TOPSPN	0.69	0.69	0.83	0.62
Developed countries				
ESUGGN	0,65	0,67	0,80	0,49
ETRAINN	0,80	0,80	0,88	0,71
INCTVN	0,86	0,86	0,91	0,78
MLTFNN	0,63	0,67	0,80	0,58
rCNATHN	0,86	0,86	0,91	0,78
TEAMSN	0,72	0,73	0,84	0,65
TOPCSN	0,61	0,61	0,80	0,56
TOPSPN	0,62	0,62	0,80	0,57
Developing countries				
ESUGGN	0,83	0,83	0,89	0,66
ETRAINN	0,78	0,78	0,87	0,69
INCTVN	0,89	0,89	0,93	0,82
MLTFNN	0,70	0,72	0,83	0,63
rCNATHN	0,75	0,75	0,86	0,67
TEAMSN	0,82	0,83	0,89	0,74
TOPCSN	0,71	0,72	0,84	0,63
TOPSPN	0,72	0,72	0,84	0,64

Table D1. Measurement model statistics total sample

Item	Composite	Original sample Loadings (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	2.5%	97.5%	Original sample weights (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	2.5%	97.5%
ESUGGN01	ESUGGN	0.77	0.05	14.94	0.00	0.69	0.83	0.35	0.03	10.77	0.00	0.30	0.41
ESUGGN02	ESUGGN	0.79	0.05	15.40	0.00	0.72	0.84	0.35	0.03	11.18	0.00	0.31	0.41
ESUGGN03	ESUGGN	0.78	0.06	13.24	0.00	0.69	0.84	0.35	0.04	8.93	0.00	0.29	0.41
ESUGGN04	ESUGGN	0.66	0.09	7.58	0.00	0.48	0.78	0.27	0.04	6.34	0.00	0.18	0.33
ETRAINN01	ETRAINN	0.86	0.02	39.87	0.00	0.81	0.89	0.41	0.01	27.45	0.00	0.38	0.44
ETRAINN02	ETRAINN	0.79	0.03	26.25	0.00	0.73	0.85	0.37	0.01	27.46	0.00	0.35	0.40
ETRAINN04	ETRAINN	0.86	0.02	42.41	0.00	0.82	0.90	0.41	0.01	30.31	0.00	0.39	0.44
INCTVN01	INCTVN	0.89	0.03	28.85	0.00	0.86	0.92	0.36	0.02	16.77	0.00	0.33	0.39
INCTVN02	INCTVN	0.91	0.03	28.49	0.00	0.87	0.94	0.38	0.02	21.83	0.00	0.35	0.40
INCTVN03	INCTVN	0.88	0.03	28.60	0.00	0.84	0.92	0.38	0.02	18.56	0.00	0.35	0.42
MLTFNN01	MLTFNN	0.84	0.02	35.93	0.00	0.79	0.88	0.48	0.03	18.12	0.00	0.44	0.54
MLTFNN02	MLTFNN	0.67	0.05	12.37	0.00	0.55	0.76	0.36	0.03	13.09	0.00	0.30	0.41
MLTFNN04	MLTFNN	0.81	0.03	26.59	0.00	0.74	0.86	0.43	0.02	17.89	0.00	0.38	0.48
rCNATHN02	rCNATHN	0.84	0.03	33.27	0.00	0.79	0.89	0.38	0.02	24.90	0.00	0.35	0.41
rCNATHN03	rCNATHN	0.88	0.02	54.37	0.00	0.85	0.91	0.39	0.01	26.30	0.00	0.36	0.42
rCNATHN04	rCNATHN	0.90	0.02	56.09	0.00	0.86	0.93	0.38	0.01	26.10	0.00	0.35	0.41
TEAMSN02	TEAMSN	0.80	0.03	24.83	0.00	0.72	0.85	0.37	0.02	17.93	0.00	0.33	0.41
TEAMSN03	TEAMSN	0.82	0.03	25.34	0.00	0.74	0.87	0.41	0.02	17.66	0.00	0.37	0.46
TEAMSN04	TEAMSN	0.87	0.02	50.21	0.00	0.83	0.90	0.42	0.02	18.95	0.00	0.39	0.47
TOPCSN01	TOPCSN	0.81	0.03	28.83	0.00	0.75	0.86	0.45	0.03	15.12	0.00	0.40	0.51
TOPCSN02	TOPCSN	0.75	0.04	18.36	0.00	0.65	0.81	0.40	0.04	10.91	0.00	0.33	0.48
TOPCSN04	TOPCSN	0.77	0.05	15.97	0.00	0.66	0.84	0.44	0.04	11.55	0.00	0.36	0.52
TOPSPN01	TOPSPN	0.79	0.04	21.48	0.00	0.70	0.85	0.42	0.03	15.69	0.00	0.37	0.48
TOPSPN02	TOPSPN	0.80	0.03	25.57	0.00	0.73	0.85	0.43	0.03	17.03	0.00	0.38	0.48
TOPSPN04	TOPSPN	0.77	0.04	20.72	0.00	0.69	0.84	0.42	0.02	16.73	0.00	0.37	0.47
ADAPT11	SC Ad	0.30	0.12	2.57	0.01	0.06	0.53	0.02	0.13	0.16	0.88	-0.23	0.27
ADAPT12	SC Ad	0.34	0.11	3.14	0.00	0.12	0.55	0.02	0.11	0.16	0.87	-0.20	0.26
ADAPT21	SC Ad	0.35	0.10	3.55	0.00	0.15	0.54	0.15	0.11	1.41	0.16	-0.07	0.35
ADAPT22	SC Ad	0.51	0.11	4.54	0.00	0.26	0.71	0.26	0.13	1.96	0.05	0.00	0.52
ADAPT31	SC Ad	0.67	0.09	7.91	0.00	0.47	0.80	0.29	0.12	2.42	0.02	0.05	0.52
ADAPT32	SC Ad	0.88	0.06	13.61	0.00	0.70	0.95	0.69	0.11	6.19	0.00	0.42	0.86
AGIL11	SC Ag	0.11	0.13	0.89	0.38	-0.15	0.35	-0.17	0.13	1.29	0.20	-0.41	0.09
AGIL12	SC Ag	0.24	0.12	2.02	0.04	-0.02	0.46	0.21	0.12	1.68	0.09	-0.05	0.44
AGIL22	SC Ag	0.78	0.07	11.11	0.00	0.60	0.88	0.54	0.10	5.36	0.00	0.32	0.71
AGIL23	SC Ag	0.76	0.07	10.23	0.00	0.57	0.86	0.51	0.11	4.88	0.00	0.28	0.70
AGIL31	SC Ag	0.38	0.11	3.34	0.00	0.13	0.57	0.15	0.12	1.24	0.21	-0.09	0.38
AGIL32	SC Ag	0.35	0.13	2.72	0.01	0.07	0.57	0.19	0.15	1.33	0.18	-0.09	0.47
AGIL33	SC Ag	0.37	0.11	3.28	0.00	0.12	0.57	0.08	0.13	0.59	0.55	-0.19	0.32

ALIGN11	SC AI	0.49	0.09	5.51	0.00	0.31	0.65	0.31	0.08	3.97	0.00	0.15	0.46
ALIGN13	SC AI	0.83	0.04	18.83	0.00	0.72	0.90	0.54	0.08	6.77	0.00	0.37	0.68
ALIGN22	SC AI	0.60	0.06	9.77	0.00	0.47	0.71	0.26	0.08	3.36	0.00	0.10	0.40
ALIGN24	SC AI	0.43	0.09	4.90	0.00	0.25	0.59	0.05	0.09	0.55	0.59	-0.13	0.23
ALIGN32	SC AI	0.61	0.08	7.96	0.00	0.44	0.74	0.28	0.08	3.45	0.00	0.12	0.43
ALIGN33	SC AI	0.56	0.08	6.96	0.00	0.39	0.70	0.09	0.09	0.96	0.34	-0.09	0.28

Table D2. Measurement model statistics in plants of the sample of developed countries

Item	Composite	Original sample Loadings(O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	2.5%	97.5%	Original sample weights (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	2.5%	97.5 %
ESUGGN01	ESUGGN	0,73	0,09	7,92	0,00	0,58	0,84	0,38	0,07	5,37	0,00	0,27	0,52
ESUGGN02	ESUGGN	0,51	0,11	4,66	0,00	0,24	0,66	0,21	0,04	5,72	0,00	0,11	0,26
ESUGGN03	ESUGGN	0,50	0,10	4,80	0,00	0,25	0,65	0,10	0,02	5,69	0,00	0,06	0,12
ESUGGN04	ESUGGN	0,47	0,10	4,50	0,00	0,20	0,61	0,08	0,02	4,72	0,00	0,04	0,11
ETRAINN01	ETRAINN	0,54	0,12	4,62	0,00	0,24	0,69	0,21	0,04	5,51	0,00	0,11	0,26
ETRAINN02	ETRAINN	0,79	0,10	7,89	0,00	0,65	0,87	0,41	0,07	5,51	0,00	0,30	0,54
ETRAINN04	ETRAINN	0,47	0,14	3,42	0,00	0,14	0,66	0,18	0,05	3,87	0,00	0,06	0,24
INCTVN01	INCTVN	0,70	0,12	5,85	0,00	0,44	0,83	0,35	0,09	3,93	0,00	0,16	0,48
INCTVN02	INCTVN	0,40	0,12	3,30	0,00	0,11	0,58	0,08	0,02	3,87	0,00	0,03	0,11
INCTVN03	INCTVN	0,36	0,15	2,42	0,02	0,02	0,60	0,15	0,05	2,93	0,00	0,02	0,23
MLTFNN01	MLTFNN	0,57	0,17	3,30	0,00	0,16	0,79	0,27	0,11	2,52	0,01	0,01	0,40
MLTFNN02	MLTFNN	0,40	0,13	2,99	0,00	0,07	0,60	0,07	0,02	3,17	0,00	0,01	0,10
MLTFNN04	MLTFNN	0,85	0,03	25,41	0,00	0,78	0,91	0,40	0,02	19,99	0,00	0,37	0,45
TEAMSN02	TEAMSN	0,80	0,04	20,57	0,00	0,71	0,87	0,24	0,01	17,69	0,00	0,22	0,27
TEAMSN03	TEAMSN	0,66	0,06	10,25	0,00	0,52	0,78	0,12	0,01	8,00	0,00	0,09	0,15
TEAMSN04	TEAMSN	0,68	0,06	10,97	0,00	0,53	0,78	0,12	0,01	10,31	0,00	0,10	0,14
TOPCSN01	TOPCSN	0,81	0,04	18,45	0,00	0,71	0,88	0,36	0,02	20,49	0,00	0,33	0,40
TOPCSN02	TOPCSN	0,72	0,05	13,99	0,00	0,60	0,80	0,22	0,01	15,19	0,00	0,19	0,25
TOPCSN04	TOPCSN	0,87	0,03	32,72	0,00	0,81	0,92	0,42	0,02	21,02	0,00	0,39	0,47
TOPSPN01	TOPSPN	0,84	0,03	30,28	0,00	0,78	0,89	0,26	0,01	17,60	0,00	0,23	0,29
TOPSPN02	TOPSPN	0,69	0,06	11,38	0,00	0,56	0,80	0,12	0,01	8,15	0,00	0,09	0,15
TOPSPN04	TOPSPN	0,74	0,06	12,13	0,00	0,61	0,86	0,28	0,03	8,58	0,00	0,22	0,35
rCNATHN02	rCNATHN	0,88	0,03	29,45	0,00	0,81	0,93	0,37	0,02	19,79	0,00	0,34	0,41
rCNATHN03	rCNATHN	0,65	0,07	9,66	0,00	0,51	0,78	0,12	0,02	7,10	0,00	0,09	0,15
rCNATHN04	rCNATHN	0,62	0,09	7,18	0,00	0,44	0,78	0,12	0,02	6,00	0,00	0,08	0,16
ADAPT11	SC Ad	0,17	0,14	1,21	0,23	-0,10	0,44	-0,03	0,13	0,19	0,85	-0,28	0,23
ADAPT12	SC Ad	0,40	0,14	2,80	0,01	0,09	0,66	0,09	0,16	0,58	0,56	-0,21	0,42
ADAPT21	SC Ad	0,38	0,14	2,77	0,01	0,09	0,62	0,10	0,13	0,75	0,45	-0,17	0,35
ADAPT22	SC Ad	0,45	0,15	2,95	0,00	0,10	0,70	0,20	0,15	1,34	0,18	-0,10	0,48
ADAPT31	SC Ad	0,74	0,11	6,96	0,00	0,47	0,89	0,34	0,17	2,02	0,04	0,02	0,68

ADAPT32	SC Ad	0,90	0,08	10,96	0,00	0,66	0,97	0,65	0,17	3,87	0,00	0,23	0,90
AGIL11	SC Ag	0,28	0,16	1,75	0,08	-0,05	0,58	-0,02	0,17	0,12	0,91	-0,37	0,30
AGIL12	SC Ag	0,30	0,15	1,96	0,05	-0,03	0,57	0,08	0,17	0,45	0,65	-0,23	0,43
AGIL22	SC Ag	0,78	0,10	7,93	0,00	0,51	0,89	0,58	0,12	4,77	0,00	0,30	0,78
AGIL23	SC Ag	0,76	0,09	8,05	0,00	0,51	0,87	0,48	0,14	3,49	0,00	0,18	0,72
AGIL31	SC Ag	0,30	0,16	1,93	0,05	-0,04	0,57	-0,02	0,16	0,11	0,91	-0,30	0,32
AGIL32	SC Ag	0,32	0,16	1,93	0,05	-0,06	0,59	0,32	0,17	1,85	0,06	-0,03	0,65
AGIL33	SC Ag	0,44	0,16	2,77	0,01	0,05	0,66	0,15	0,18	0,84	0,40	-0,27	0,45
ALIGN11	SC Al	0,55	0,14	4,02	0,00	0,25	0,78	0,42	0,11	3,97	0,00	0,21	0,62
ALIGN13	SC Al	0,72	0,08	8,77	0,00	0,52	0,85	0,39	0,10	3,91	0,00	0,17	0,56
ALIGN22	SC Al	0,62	0,08	7,73	0,00	0,43	0,75	0,13	0,09	1,38	0,17	-0,08	0,29
ALIGN24	SC Al	0,59	0,10	6,11	0,00	0,38	0,75	0,24	0,12	2,10	0,04	0,02	0,48
ALIGN32	SC Al	0,63	0,11	5,55	0,00	0,37	0,80	0,25	0,12	2,16	0,03	0,02	0,48
ALIGN33	SC Al	0,61	0,12	5,28	0,00	0,34	0,79	0,17	0,13	1,31	0,19	-0,08	0,42

Table D3. Measurement model statistics in plants of the sample of developing countries

Item	Composite	Original sample Loadings (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	2.5%	97.5%	Original sample weights (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	2.5%	97.5%
ESUGGN01	ESUGGN	0,83	0,05	17,04	0,00	0,76	0,88	0,31	0,02	12,94	0,00	0,27	0,34
ESUGGN02	ESUGGN	0,69	0,08	8,73	0,00	0,53	0,83	0,24	0,03	7,35	0,00	0,19	0,31
ESUGGN03	ESUGGN	0,62	0,08	8,24	0,00	0,46	0,74	0,12	0,02	6,91	0,00	0,09	0,15
ESUGGN04	ESUGGN	0,61	0,07	8,66	0,00	0,46	0,72	0,11	0,02	7,37	0,00	0,09	0,15
ETRAINN01	ETRAINN	0,68	0,07	9,81	0,00	0,55	0,80	0,24	0,03	7,83	0,00	0,19	0,30
ETRAINN02	ETRAINN	0,80	0,05	16,15	0,00	0,72	0,86	0,30	0,02	12,18	0,00	0,27	0,35
ETRAINN04	ETRAINN	0,75	0,07	11,32	0,00	0,62	0,85	0,25	0,03	8,03	0,00	0,20	0,32
INCTVN01	INCTVN	0,85	0,05	18,77	0,00	0,79	0,89	0,33	0,03	12,22	0,00	0,29	0,38
INCTVN02	INCTVN	0,62	0,07	8,62	0,00	0,47	0,73	0,11	0,02	6,81	0,00	0,09	0,15
INCTVN03	INCTVN	0,66	0,09	7,52	0,00	0,48	0,80	0,24	0,03	6,92	0,00	0,18	0,31
MLTFNN01	MLTFNN	0,78	0,06	12,33	0,00	0,66	0,87	0,29	0,02	12,04	0,00	0,25	0,33
MLTFNN02	MLTFNN	0,66	0,08	8,45	0,00	0,50	0,78	0,13	0,02	7,02	0,00	0,10	0,17
MLTFNN04	MLTFNN	0,86	0,03	32,15	0,00	0,80	0,91	0,42	0,02	17,95	0,00	0,38	0,47
TEAMSN02	TEAMSN	0,78	0,04	18,58	0,00	0,68	0,84	0,26	0,02	14,09	0,00	0,23	0,30
TEAMSN03	TEAMSN	0,55	0,11	4,99	0,00	0,28	0,68	0,10	0,02	5,29	0,00	0,06	0,13
TEAMSN04	TEAMSN	0,60	0,09	6,36	0,00	0,37	0,71	0,11	0,02	6,49	0,00	0,08	0,14
TOPCSN01	TOPCSN	0,78	0,05	16,68	0,00	0,66	0,85	0,38	0,02	15,46	0,00	0,33	0,43
TOPCSN02	TOPCSN	0,71	0,06	12,22	0,00	0,57	0,80	0,24	0,02	12,31	0,00	0,21	0,28
TOPCSN04	TOPCSN	0,86	0,03	27,89	0,00	0,79	0,90	0,40	0,02	20,50	0,00	0,37	0,45
TOPSPN01	TOPSPN	0,74	0,05	16,04	0,00	0,64	0,82	0,25	0,02	14,28	0,00	0,22	0,29
TOPSPN02	TOPSPN	0,57	0,09	6,28	0,00	0,35	0,68	0,11	0,02	6,69	0,00	0,08	0,13
TOPSPN04	TOPSPN	0,53	0,20	2,59	0,01	-0,08	0,71	0,19	0,07	2,82	0,00	-0,02	0,25
rCNATHN02	rCNATHN	0,90	0,25	3,61	0,00	0,73	0,94	0,35	0,13	2,75	0,01	-0,03	0,41

rCNATHN03	rCNATHN	0,43	0,15	2,85	0,00	0,04	0,62	0,08	0,03	2,78	0,01	0,00	0,12
rCNATHN04	rCNATHN	0,48	0,14	3,34	0,00	0,08	0,65	0,09	0,03	3,27	0,00	0,01	0,12
ADAPT11	SC Ad	0,41	0,20	2,07	0,04	-0,05	0,72	0,12	0,23	0,55	0,59	-0,35	0,54
ADAPT12	SC Ad	0,29	0,16	1,82	0,07	-0,04	0,56	-0,07	0,18	0,37	0,71	-0,39	0,29
ADAPT21	SC Ad	0,27	0,17	1,56	0,12	-0,07	0,61	0,14	0,18	0,77	0,44	-0,22	0,50
ADAPT22	SC Ad	0,52	0,20	2,53	0,01	0,06	0,84	0,26	0,24	1,08	0,28	-0,22	0,74
ADAPT31	SC Ad	0,59	0,18	3,31	0,00	0,13	0,79	0,21	0,20	1,01	0,31	-0,23	0,57
ADAPT32	SC Ad	0,89	0,18	5,01	0,00	0,30	0,96	0,75	0,23	3,30	0,00	0,06	0,97
AGIL11	SC Ag	-0,14	0,18	0,77	0,44	-0,46	0,24	-0,35	0,19	1,83	0,07	-0,68	0,06
AGIL12	SC Ag	0,05	0,19	0,26	0,80	-0,32	0,42	0,22	0,20	1,10	0,27	-0,19	0,58
AGIL22	SC Ag	0,75	0,13	5,60	0,00	0,42	0,89	0,55	0,16	3,35	0,00	0,19	0,80
AGIL23	SC Ag	0,73	0,14	5,22	0,00	0,37	0,86	0,51	0,16	3,22	0,00	0,13	0,74
AGIL31	SC Ag	0,42	0,14	2,90	0,00	0,09	0,66	0,36	0,15	2,42	0,02	0,04	0,62
AGIL32	SC Ag	0,33	0,17	1,89	0,06	-0,04	0,63	-0,08	0,21	0,37	0,71	-0,45	0,36
AGIL33	SC Ag	0,28	0,14	1,94	0,05	-0,03	0,53	0,09	0,16	0,52	0,60	-0,25	0,39
ALIGN11	SC AI	0,38	0,13	2,87	0,00	0,08	0,60	0,16	0,12	1,36	0,17	-0,07	0,37
ALIGN13	SC AI	0,90	0,06	14,32	0,00	0,74	0,95	0,70	0,11	6,17	0,00	0,44	0,88
ALIGN22	SC AI	0,57	0,11	5,39	0,00	0,35	0,74	0,29	0,11	2,57	0,01	0,07	0,51
ALIGN24	SC AI	0,28	0,14	2,00	0,05	0,00	0,54	-0,12	0,13	0,96	0,34	-0,37	0,13
ALIGN32	SC AI	0,60	0,09	6,44	0,00	0,39	0,74	0,26	0,10	2,51	0,01	0,06	0,46
ALIGN33	SC AI	0,50	0,12	4,01	0,00	0,21	0,68	0,05	0,14	0,38	0,71	-0,23	0,31

Table E. CVPAT's results

	PLS vs Indicator average Average loss difference	t value	p value	PLS vs Linear model Average loss difference	t value	p value
Global sample						
SC Ad	-0,06	3,59	0,00	-0,06	3,66	0,00
SC Ag	-0,03	2,73	0,01	-0,09	6,34	0,00
SC AI	-0,10	6,16	0,00	-0,01	0,77	0,44
Developed countries						
SC Ad	-0,07	3,10	0,00	-0,11	3,89	0,00
SC Ag	-0,11	4,83	0,00	-0,15	5,90	0,00
SC AI	-0,12	5,35	0,00	-0,04	1,50	0,14
Developing countries						
SC Ad	-0,12	3,45	0,00	-0,22	5,21	0,00
SC Ag	-0,01	1,11	0,27	-0,19	4,86	0,00
SC AI	-0,08	3,30	0,00	-0,09	4,14	0,00

Table F. Permutation Multigroup Analysis path's results

	Original (Developed)	Original (Developing)	Original difference	Permutation mean difference	2.5%	97.5%	Permutation p value
AMO -> Ad	0,21	0,11	0,11	0,00	-0,27	0,28	0,46
AMO -> Ag	0,22	-0,04	0,26	0,00	-0,25	0,25	0,04
AMO -> AI	0,26	0,07	0,18	0,00	-0,18	0,19	0,05
SCO -> Ad	0,51	0,43	0,07	0,00	-0,28	0,26	0,60
SCO -> Ag	0,44	0,50	-0,06	0,00	-0,21	0,22	0,60
SCO -> AI	0,60	0,63	-0,03	0,00	-0,15	0,15	0,69

Table G. MICOM results

	Step2	Step3.Mean				Step3.Variance			
	Permutation p value	Original difference	2.5%	97.5%	Permutation p value	Original difference	2.5%	97.5%	Permutation p value
Ad	0,96	0,22	-0,23	0,23	0,07	-0,05	-0,43	0,41	0,81
Ag	0,53	-0,02	-0,23	0,22	0,83	0,13	-0,42	0,41	0,55
AI	0,13	0,28	-0,23	0,23	0,02	-0,11	-0,33	0,32	0,50
ESUGGN	0,60	0,03	-0,23	0,24	0,82	-0,02	-0,37	0,36	0,92
ETRAINN	0,46	-0,11	-0,23	0,24	0,36	0,37	-0,47	0,46	0,13
INCTVN	0,30	0,42	-0,23	0,24	0,00	0,05	-0,34	0,33	0,76
MLTFNN	0,15	-0,36	-0,23	0,24	0,00	0,36	-0,37	0,36	0,06
TEAMSN	0,66	-0,04	-0,23	0,23	0,73	-0,01	-0,35	0,35	0,97
TOPCSN	0,39	0,04	-0,23	0,23	0,75	-0,11	-0,43	0,43	0,68
TOPSPN	0,79	0,41	-0,23	0,23	0,00	-0,39	-0,38	0,36	0,04
rCNATHN	0,75	-0,81	-0,23	0,23	0,00	0,97	-0,34	0,32	0,00

Table H. PLS-Predict results

	Q ² predict	PLS-SEM_RMSE	PLS-SEM_MAE	LM_RMSE	LM_MAE
Global sample					
ADAPT11	-0,01	1,01	0,78	1,08	0,83
ADAPT12	0,00	1,09	0,87	1,15	0,94
ADAPT21	0,14	0,64	0,49	0,66	0,50
ADAPT22	0,13	0,65	0,47	0,67	0,50
ADAPT31	0,03	0,89	0,61	0,93	0,68
ADAPT32	0,02	1,01	0,87	1,07	0,91
AGIL11	0,02	0,91	0,65	0,96	0,72
AGIL12	0,10	0,87	0,71	0,84	0,65
AGIL22	0,31	0,75	0,58	0,79	0,60
AGIL23	0,16	0,66	0,52	0,66	0,51
AGIL31	0,08	0,65	0,54	0,65	0,51

AGIL32	0,16	0,60	0,47	0,61	0,47
AGIL33	0,13	0,73	0,52	0,75	0,55
ALIGN11	-0,01	1,01	0,78	1,08	0,83
ALIGN13	0,00	1,09	0,87	1,15	0,94
ALIGN22	0,14	0,64	0,49	0,66	0,50
ALIGN24	0,13	0,65	0,47	0,67	0,50
ALIGN32	0,03	0,89	0,61	0,93	0,68
ALIGN33	0,02	1,01	0,87	1,07	0,91
Developed countries					
ADAPT11	0,04	0,92	0,69	1,01	0,77
ADAPT12	0,12	0,79	0,59	0,84	0,64
ADAPT21	0,09	0,81	0,63	0,89	0,71
ADAPT22	0,10	0,92	0,72	0,97	0,74
ADAPT31	0,14	0,88	0,68	0,96	0,74
ADAPT32	0,10	0,65	0,49	0,68	0,50
AGIL11	0,02	1,06	0,86	1,21	0,97
AGIL12	0,07	1,08	0,88	1,19	0,97
AGIL22	0,32	0,63	0,46	0,63	0,46
AGIL23	0,28	0,66	0,51	0,70	0,53
AGIL31	0,16	0,83	0,61	0,92	0,67
AGIL32	0,08	0,98	0,82	1,02	0,85
AGIL33	0,13	0,88	0,67	0,99	0,75
ALIGN11	0,07	0,96	0,79	0,93	0,72
ALIGN13	0,30	0,80	0,61	0,87	0,67
ALIGN22	0,23	0,66	0,51	0,69	0,54
ALIGN24	0,08	0,68	0,54	0,70	0,54
ALIGN32	0,26	0,56	0,44	0,55	0,44
ALIGN33	0,13	0,78	0,58	0,84	0,63
Developing countries					
ADAPT11	-0,01	0,82	0,62	0,95	0,76
ADAPT12	-0,01	0,86	0,61	0,96	0,75
ADAPT21	0,02	0,90	0,72	1,10	0,87
ADAPT22	0,10	0,93	0,76	1,02	0,81
ADAPT31	0,27	0,77	0,57	0,86	0,67
ADAPT32	0,47	0,67	0,48	0,78	0,58
AGIL11	0,00	0,91	0,68	1,03	0,84
AGIL12	-0,02	1,08	0,86	1,22	0,97
AGIL22	0,13	0,55	0,41	0,63	0,48
AGIL23	0,11	0,53	0,35	0,57	0,43
AGIL31	0,01	0,89	0,65	0,90	0,68
AGIL32	0,01	1,03	0,89	1,22	1,00
AGIL33	-0,01	0,89	0,61	1,01	0,77

ALIGN11	0,15	0,73	0,59	0,81	0,63
ALIGN13	0,37	0,66	0,52	0,71	0,57
ALIGN22	0,11	0,62	0,51	0,66	0,52
ALIGN24	0,06	0,62	0,53	0,69	0,56
ALIGN32	0,06	0,66	0,51	0,72	0,55
ALIGN33	0,10	0,67	0,45	0,76	0,55

Table J1. Descriptive statistics for LOC and HOC

	Mean	Observed min	Observed max	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
Total sample 287 plants						
AMO	3,86	2,17	4,95	0,44	0,66	-0,37
Ability	3,90	1,94	5,00	0,55	0,98	-0,69
Ad	3,93	1,61	5,00	0,60	1,31	-0,84
Ag	3,95	2,08	5,00	0,50	1,17	-0,66
AI	3,98	2,51	5,00	0,52	-0,04	-0,42
ESUGGN	3,97	1,29	5,00	0,62	0,64	-0,66
ETRAINN	3,99	1,00	5,00	0,64	2,04	-1,01
INCTVN	3,61	1,00	5,00	0,81	0,06	-0,61
MLTFNN	3,79	1,70	5,00	0,59	0,47	-0,50
Motivation	3,81	1,60	5,00	0,53	0,55	-0,43
Opportunity	3,82	2,33	5,00	0,61	-0,51	-0,26
SCO	4,14	2,63	5,00	0,48	0,44	-0,61
TEAMSN	3,89	1,30	5,00	0,68	0,32	-0,47
TOPCSN	4,26	1,64	5,00	0,53	1,65	-0,81
TOPSPN	4,00	2,00	5,00	0,66	0,54	-0,71
rCNATHN	3,72	1,16	5,00	0,93	-0,02	-0,76
Developed countries' sample : 133 plants						
AMO	3,83	2,12	4,96	0,48	0,40	-0,12
Ability	3,83	1,91	5,00	0,61	0,36	-0,44
Ad	4,00	1,71	5,00	0,60	2,35	-1,10
Ag	3,96	2,31	5,00	0,50	0,93	-0,53
AI	4,07	2,89	5,00	0,47	-0,16	-0,25
ESUGGN	3,99	2,12	5,00	0,61	-0,21	-0,52
ETRAINN	3,95	1,00	5,00	0,70	1,61	-0,79
INCTVN	3,79	1,00	5,00	0,80	1,24	-0,87
MLTFNN	3,67	1,69	5,00	0,64	0,16	-0,23
Motivation	3,89	2,25	5,00	0,55	0,05	-0,34
Opportunity	3,66	2,32	5,00	0,65	-0,61	0,02
SCO	4,21	2,60	5,00	0,47	1,08	-0,88
TEAMSN	3,88	1,33	5,00	0,68	0,70	-0,42

TOPCSN	4,27	2,44	5,00	0,52	0,26	-0,48
TOPSPN	4,15	2,00	5,00	0,58	1,86	-1,02
rCNATHN	3,32	1,16	5,00	1,04	-0,84	-0,23
Developing countries' sample : 154 Plants						
AMO	3,91	2,31	4,83	0,40	1,35	-0,71
Ability	3,97	2,00	5,00	0,48	1,96	-0,92
Ad	3,86	1,51	5,00	0,62	1,24	-0,77
Ag	4,04	2,21	5,29	0,52	0,77	-0,56
AI	3,90	2,38	5,00	0,60	-0,18	-0,50
ESUGGN	3,96	1,28	5,00	0,62	1,39	-0,81
ETRAINN	4,02	2,00	5,00	0,58	2,46	-1,26
INCTVN	3,45	1,64	5,00	0,79	-0,60	-0,50
MLTFNN	3,90	2,00	5,00	0,53	1,08	-0,73
Motivation	3,78	1,53	4,86	0,51	1,50	-0,74
Opportunity	3,98	2,51	5,00	0,52	-0,33	-0,34
SCO	4,08	2,63	5,00	0,48	0,32	-0,46
TEAMSN	3,90	2,00	5,00	0,68	0,07	-0,51
TOPCSN	4,26	1,62	5,00	0,55	2,82	-1,09
TOPSPN	3,87	2,00	5,00	0,70	0,02	-0,44
rCNATHN	4,07	2,00	5,00	0,64	0,62	-0,77

Table J2. Correlations for LOC and HOC

Total sample	AMO	Ability	Ad	Ag	AI	ESUGGN	ETRAINN	INCTVN	MLTFNN	Motivation	Opportunity	SCO	TEAMSN	TOPCSN	TOPSPN	rCNATHN
AMO	1,00	0,80	0,30	0,27	0,35	0,68	0,76	0,62	0,66	0,85	0,65	0,32	0,64	0,26	0,26	0,36
Ability	0,80	1,00	0,25	0,19	0,31	0,24	0,92	0,53	0,87	0,51	0,24	0,29	0,21	0,23	0,23	0,17
Ad	0,30	0,25	1,00	0,24	0,36	0,21	0,23	0,19	0,22	0,26	0,18	0,53	0,19	0,56	0,31	0,08
Ag	0,27	0,19	0,24	1,00	0,51	0,20	0,12	0,19	0,23	0,26	0,17	0,48	0,21	0,29	0,48	0,06
AI	0,35	0,31	0,36	0,51	1,00	0,20	0,26	0,26	0,30	0,30	0,17	0,67	0,16	0,46	0,61	0,10
ESUGGN	0,68	0,24	0,21	0,20	0,20	1,00	0,25	0,15	0,17	0,75	0,60	0,23	0,69	0,19	0,18	0,24
ETRAINN	0,76	0,92	0,23	0,12	0,26	0,25	1,00	0,53	0,60	0,52	0,23	0,22	0,21	0,18	0,18	0,15
INCTVN	0,62	0,53	0,19	0,19	0,26	0,15	0,53	1,00	0,41	0,77	0,02	0,23	0,12	0,13	0,25	-0,09
MLTFNN	0,66	0,87	0,22	0,23	0,30	0,17	0,60	0,41	1,00	0,38	0,21	0,30	0,16	0,25	0,23	0,16
Motivation	0,85	0,51	0,26	0,26	0,30	0,75	0,52	0,77	0,38	1,00	0,41	0,31	0,53	0,21	0,28	0,10
Opportunity	0,65	0,24	0,18	0,17	0,17	0,60	0,23	0,02	0,21	0,41	1,00	0,13	0,79	0,15	0,06	0,77
SCO	0,32	0,29	0,53	0,48	0,67	0,23	0,22	0,23	0,30	0,31	0,13	1,00	0,14	0,79	0,82	0,06
TEAMSN	0,64	0,21	0,19	0,21	0,16	0,69	0,21	0,12	0,16	0,53	0,79	0,14	1,00	0,16	0,07	0,21
TOPCSN	0,26	0,23	0,56	0,29	0,46	0,19	0,18	0,13	0,25	0,21	0,15	0,79	0,16	1,00	0,29	0,06
TOPSPN	0,26	0,23	0,31	0,48	0,61	0,18	0,18	0,25	0,23	0,28	0,06	0,82	0,07	0,29	1,00	0,03
rCNATHN	0,36	0,17	0,08	0,06	0,10	0,24	0,15	-0,09	0,16	0,10	0,77	0,06	0,21	0,06	0,03	1,00
Developed	AMO	Ability	Ad	Ag	AI	ESUGGN	ETRAINN	INCTVN	MLTFNN	Motivation	Opportunity	SCO	TEAMSN	TOPCSN	TOPSPN	rCNATHN

AMO	1,00	0,84	0,44	0,42	0,52	0,63	0,80	0,76	0,74	0,91	0,57	0,44	0,63	0,36	0,40	0,28
Ability	0,84	1,00	0,33	0,28	0,45	0,24	0,93	0,71	0,89	0,66	0,19	0,36	0,22	0,27	0,35	0,08
Ad	0,44	0,33	1,00	0,32	0,43	0,29	0,32	0,34	0,29	0,41	0,29	0,60	0,30	0,59	0,44	0,15
Ag	0,42	0,28	0,32	1,00	0,54	0,30	0,25	0,34	0,26	0,42	0,28	0,54	0,37	0,40	0,52	0,07
AI	0,52	0,45	0,43	0,54	1,00	0,37	0,41	0,30	0,41	0,42	0,34	0,71	0,35	0,56	0,67	0,19
ESUGGN	0,63	0,24	0,29	0,30	0,37	1,00	0,22	0,19	0,23	0,68	0,63	0,34	0,76	0,32	0,27	0,24
ETRAINN	0,80	0,93	0,32	0,25	0,41	0,22	1,00	0,69	0,67	0,64	0,18	0,31	0,21	0,23	0,29	0,07
INCTVN	0,76	0,71	0,34	0,34	0,30	0,19	0,69	1,00	0,59	0,85	0,11	0,28	0,21	0,24	0,24	-0,04
MLTFNN	0,74	0,89	0,29	0,26	0,41	0,23	0,67	0,59	1,00	0,57	0,16	0,37	0,19	0,28	0,35	0,06
Motivation	0,91	0,66	0,41	0,42	0,42	0,68	0,64	0,85	0,57	1,00	0,42	0,39	0,57	0,35	0,32	0,10
Opportunity	0,57	0,19	0,29	0,28	0,34	0,63	0,18	0,11	0,16	0,42	1,00	0,27	0,78	0,19	0,27	0,79
SCO	0,44	0,36	0,60	0,54	0,71	0,34	0,31	0,28	0,37	0,39	0,27	1,00	0,30	0,86	0,87	0,12
TEAMSN	0,63	0,22	0,30	0,37	0,35	0,76	0,21	0,21	0,19	0,57	0,78	0,30	1,00	0,26	0,26	0,23
TOPCSN	0,36	0,27	0,59	0,40	0,56	0,32	0,23	0,24	0,28	0,35	0,19	0,86	0,26	1,00	0,48	0,04
TOPSPN	0,40	0,35	0,44	0,52	0,67	0,27	0,29	0,24	0,35	0,32	0,27	0,87	0,26	0,48	1,00	0,17
rCNATHN	0,28	0,08	0,15	0,07	0,19	0,24	0,07	-0,04	0,06	0,10	0,79	0,12	0,23	0,04	0,17	1,00
Developing	AMO	Ability	Ad	Ag	AI	ESUGGN	ETRAINN	INCTVN	MLTFNN	Motivation	Opportunity	SCO	TEAMSN	TOPCSN	TOPSPN	rCNATHN
AMO	1,00	0,71	0,21	0,08	0,22	0,77	0,69	0,49	0,54	0,86	0,76	0,23	0,68	0,19	0,18	0,49
Ability	0,71	1,00	0,22	0,07	0,24	0,25	0,89	0,44	0,84	0,43	0,27	0,26	0,20	0,21	0,20	0,22
Ad	0,21	0,22	1,00	0,18	0,30	0,14	0,16	0,03	0,22	0,13	0,14	0,46	0,10	0,53	0,19	0,12
Ag	0,08	0,07	0,18	1,00	0,48	0,07	-0,01	0,07	0,16	0,09	0,02	0,49	0,01	0,23	0,50	0,03
AI	0,22	0,24	0,30	0,48	1,00	0,08	0,13	0,19	0,29	0,16	0,13	0,65	0,06	0,41	0,58	0,15
ESUGGN	0,77	0,25	0,14	0,07	0,08	1,00	0,29	0,12	0,13	0,85	0,64	0,14	0,64	0,10	0,12	0,32
ETRAINN	0,69	0,89	0,16	-0,01	0,13	0,29	1,00	0,42	0,51	0,45	0,28	0,16	0,21	0,13	0,13	0,23
INCTVN	0,49	0,44	0,03	0,07	0,19	0,12	0,42	1,00	0,34	0,62	0,07	0,15	0,06	0,03	0,20	0,05
MLTFNN	0,54	0,84	0,22	0,16	0,29	0,13	0,51	0,34	1,00	0,28	0,18	0,30	0,13	0,25	0,22	0,15
Motivation	0,86	0,43	0,13	0,09	0,16	0,85	0,45	0,62	0,28	1,00	0,54	0,19	0,54	0,09	0,20	0,28
Opportunity	0,76	0,27	0,14	0,02	0,13	0,64	0,28	0,07	0,18	0,54	1,00	0,10	0,84	0,14	0,02	0,71
SCO	0,23	0,26	0,46	0,49	0,65	0,14	0,16	0,15	0,30	0,19	0,10	1,00	0,03	0,74	0,80	0,14
TEAMSN	0,68	0,20	0,10	0,01	0,06	0,64	0,21	0,06	0,13	0,54	0,84	0,03	1,00	0,09	-0,05	0,22
TOPCSN	0,19	0,21	0,53	0,23	0,41	0,10	0,13	0,03	0,25	0,09	0,14	0,74	0,09	1,00	0,18	0,13
TOPSPN	0,18	0,20	0,19	0,50	0,58	0,12	0,13	0,20	0,22	0,20	0,02	0,80	-0,05	0,18	1,00	0,09
rCNATHN	0,49	0,22	0,12	0,03	0,15	0,32	0,23	0,05	0,15	0,28	0,71	0,14	0,22	0,13	0,09	1,00

APPENDIX B. METHODS (Extended version of Section 3)

3. METHODS

3.1 Sample and data collection

The data set used in this research has been taken from the database of the 4th round of the High-Performance Manufacturing (HPM) research project¹. A random sample was drawn from master lists of plants with a minimum of 100 workers, in the machinery, electronics, and automotive components industries in 14 different countries (9 developed countries (Austria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Japan, Spain, Sweden, UK, USA) and five developing countries (Brazil, China, South Korea, Taiwan, Vietnam)). These sectors were chosen as there are such multiple plants in all the countries and are subject to fierce worldwide competition in a variety of environments (Garrido-Vega et al., 2015; Morita et al., 2018). The worldwide variety of countries makes this study's results more generalizable, as extrapolation is more limited when the scope of the sample is only national or regional.

Non-response bias was limited by a response rate of approximately 65%. There was a total of 12 questionnaires used in this research which were distributed to the plant manager and two SC and 2 HR managers in order for the questions to be answered by multiple respondents (Danese et al., 2019). In addition, different people responded to questions related to the dependent and independent variables (for further information, see Marin-Garcia et al. (2018), Danese et al. (2019), and Machuca et al. (2021)).

Several steps were taken to reduce the risk of common method bias (Schwarz et al., 2017): Items were randomly listed in scales to prevent item proximity generating any response patterns (Marin-Garcia et al., 2018); the

¹ The High Performance Manufacturing (HPM) project was launched by Roger Schroeder and Barbara Flynn. Its first round included 45 plants (American and Japanese-owned US plants) in three industrial sectors (automotive components, equipment/machinery and electronics) These sectors were chosen as there are such multiple plants in all the countries and are subject to fierce worldwide competition in a variety of environments (Garrido-Vega et al., 2015; Morita et al., 2018). The survey began in 1989 and finished in 1991. The questionnaires were modified in the successive rounds and new countries (Canada, Germany, Japan, Italy and the United Kingdom) were added for the second one (1997–1999) to create a more international database (Schroeder and Flynn, 2001). As a consequence, 164 plants were analysed in Asia (Japan), Europe (UK, Germany and Italy) and North America (US/Canada). Questionnaires were further updated in the third round (2006–2009) and data were taken from 266 plants in the same industrial sectors in ten different countries (Germany, Austria, Korea, US/Canada, Spain, Finland, Italy, Japan and Sweden). Finally, the 4th round increased the number of participating countries and updated the scales. 287 plants were surveyed in 14 countries (9 developed countries (Austria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Japan, Spain, Sweden, UK, USA) and five emerging countries (Brazil, China, South Korea, Taiwan, Vietnam)).

questionnaires were responded to by two people in each function and they were not informed as to what the items were intended to measure before they saw them (Danese et al., 2019). In addition, Harman's Single-Factor test (Schwarz et al., 2017) was applied after the data had been collected. The correlation matrix was analyzed using a principal component with varimax rotation. The results obtained were robust and valid and indicated that 8 different factors were present with eigenvalues above 1. For further details regarding HPM Round 4 questionnaires, please see Flynn et al., 1995; Schroeder and Flynn, 2001; Danese et al., 2019; Machuca et al., 2021, or Beraldin et al., 2022, inter alia.

The final HPM data set used was composed of 330 plant responses. We proceeded with two-step missing treatment. In the first step, the nearest neighbor procedure was used (Hair et al., 2009) for each case if the lower order construct had at least half of the items with values. The mean of these values was inputted for missing data. Plants were discarded if they had missing values in more than 15% of the items included in our study (Hair et al., 2019a). At this point, all the variables had fewer than 5% of values missing per item. The final sample for analysis consisted of 287 plants (133 from developed and 154 from developing countries) with missing values completely at random (MCAR) (Little test, sig 0.166 using SPSS (IBM Corp. 2013) MVA procedure). In the second step, the SmartPLS 4.0.8.8 mean replacement option was selected (Hair et al., 2019a; Hair et al., 2022). The final sample of 287 plants in the three mentioned sectors (electronics (100), machinery (109), and automotive components (78)). The sample comprised 133 plants in developed countries and 154 plants in developing countries.

Due to a lack of previous studies that have reported Triple-A SC components' estimated R² based on AMO or SCOTMS, we have considered a value of 0.1 as the expected R² for the exogenous construct (adaptability, agility, alignment) as this represents the minimum value that covers 90.6% of the generic results for operations found by Bayonne et al. (2020). Using G-Power 3.1, the minimum sample size required was 143 for the lowest forecast value of R² with Alpha 5% and Power 80% (Marin-Garcia and Alfalla-Luque, 2019). A post hoc power check with R²=0.25 (the lowest value in our analysis) shows a result of 0.99 power.

3.2. Measurement instrument

AMO has been operationalized (Marin-Garcia and Martinez Tomas, 2016) as a reflective-reflective Higher Order Composite (HOC) (Sarstedt et al., 2019) estimated from the three dimensions in which the HR practices that it contains are usually grouped (ability, motivation, and opportunity). This follows the present widespread current that considers AMO a latent model where the overall latent construct leads to various dimensions of the construct and where the dimensions are different ways in which the construct is assembled. AMO is defined in terms of the commonality among the dimensions, although these must at the same time also present discriminant validity. In this case, it is considered that all the dimensions must be present in the plant for it to be considered to possess AMO.

Ability has been formulated as a second order reflective composite estimated from two reflective Lower Order composites (LOC) with three items each: Task-related Training for Employees (ETRAIN) and multifunction employees (MLTFNN). The related questions were answered by the plant's Human Resources Manager. Motivation is a reflective composite estimated from two reflective LOC: Goal-Based Incentives (INCTVN) (answered by the plant's Human Resources Manager) and Employee Suggestions Implementation and Feedback (ESUGGN) with 4 items (answered by the plant supervisor). Opportunity is a reflective composite estimated from two reflective LOC: Small Group Problem Solving (TEAMSN) (with 3 items answered by the plant supervisor) and decentralization of Authority (rCNATHN) with three reversed items from the direct labor responses. SCO is operationalized as a second-order reflective composite with two LOC adapted from Min et al. (2007) with two items each: SCO-TMS to customers (TOPCSN) and SCO-TMS to suppliers (TOPSPN). The items corresponding to the first of these were answered by SC managers. All the items in this research come from the scales used in the HPM project 4th Round, which had been validated and used in previous rounds of the Project. Appendix A-Table B in the online supplementary material gives the codes for the items used.

Mutually complementary items validated in previous research were selected for each of the formative lower order composites (SC agility (SC-Ag), SC adaptability (SC-Ad), and SC alignment (SC-AI)) (Marin-Garcia et al., 2018). SC-Ag, SC-Ad, and SC-AI composite constructs were estimated as Mode B (Regression weights). This part of the

questionnaire was answered by the SC managers who responded to all the Lower Order Composite items on a 5-point Likert measurement scale (1–strongly disagree, 3–neither agree nor disagree, 5–strongly agree).

Following Machuca et al. (2021), this study used control variables supported by prior research on SCM (Gligor et al., 2015; Dubey and Gunasekaran, 2016; Dubey et al., 2019; Alfalla-Luque et al., 2023). These include: a) plant size (log10), since larger organizations could use economies of scale to enhance their competitive position by implementing some concrete SC practices (Gligor et al., 2015; Dubey et al., 2019; Machuca et al., 2021); b) industry, since some industries be in a more uncertain environment than others (e.g., more or less stable customer preferences or product characteristics) (Dubey et al., 2019; Machuca et al., 2021; Alfalla-Luque et al., 2023); c) country context, since research has shown that there might be differences between developed and developing countries, with behaviors in firms in these two groups diverging on account of contextual factors such as labor force, culture, and infrastructure, inter alia (Machuca et al., 2021; Alfalla-Luque et al., 2023).

3.3. Analysis method

Partial Least Squares (PLS) (Henseler et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2019b; Hair and Sarstedt, 2019; Marin-Garcia and Alfalla-Luque, 2019; Hair et al., 2022) has been used to estimate analyzed model using SmartPLS 4.0.8.8 (Ringle et al., 2022). The main advantages of using PLS-SEM in this study are that: a) it is able to manage both reflective and formatively specified composites in the same model (Hair et al., 2019a; Marin-Garcia and Alfalla-Luque, 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2019), as is the case in this research; b) When the constructs respond to a composite measurement model, as in our case, the estimates reached by PLS-SEM are consistent and unbiased and are preferable to other methods. This has been verified in studies performed by simulations (e.g.: Sarstedt et al., 2016); c) PLS enables latent variable scores to be calculated for subsequent important analyses such as predictive capacity (Shmueli et al. 2019), and the Cross-Validated Predictive Ability Test -CVPAT (Liengard et al., 2021). This is very important in this study as it has a dual causal-predictive purpose. The predictive analysis enhances the retrospective character of explanatory models that dominate the field with prediction and helps build theories for explanation and prediction (Liengard et al., 2021). Regarding the predictive character of our research, it is necessary to point out that this purpose can only be done with PLS-SEM or another composite-based SEM method (see Rigdon, 2012; Rigdon,

2016; Rigdon et al., 2019a, 2019b). A model's predictive capacity is particularly important as it is a major indication of its aptness for offering more generalizable managerial recommendations to improve decision-making (Chin et al., 2020). This is made possible when the measure of the in-sample and out-of-sample predictive capacity shows positive results, which indicates the generation of sufficiently accurate predictions of new temporal and cross-sectional observations (Shmueli et al., 2019; Marin-Garcia et al., 2023). This measure is made possible by using PLSpredict (Cepeda et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2024), which results can be confirmed by a further analysis with Cross-Validated Predictive Ability Test (CVPAT) (Lienggaard et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). Besides, using PLSpredict involves a compromise between prediction and explanation to avoid overfit (Chin et al., 2020).

A three-stage analysis was conducted with extended repeated indicator method (Sarstedt et al., 2019) as it facilitates HOC modeling when none of the HOCs acts as a dependent construct in the path model, as is the case here. In the first stage, the measurement model for the lower order constructs was assessed (Hair et al., 2019b; Marin-Garcia and Alfalla-Luque, 2019). In the second stage, structural model was assessed (Henseler et al., 2015; Cepeda-Carrion et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2019c; Ringle et al., 2020; Becker et al., 2022; Ciavolino et al., 2022). Given that model fit measures can be useful in other modeling situations, we report the SRMR results in line with current guidelines (Cho et al., 2020).

Lastly, in the third stage, we tested the models' *out-of-sample predictive capacity*. For this, we used the PLSpredict algorithm to measure the accuracy of the models' predictions, and the prediction-error summary statistics were used to evaluate the PLS path models' predictive capacity for the indicators (Marin-Garcia and Alfalla-Luque, 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2019). 10 repetitions with 10 folds were used for the PLSpredict procedure. The PLS model was compared to the linear model (Shmueli et al., 2019). MAE (mean absolute error) and RMSE (root mean square error) are particularly suitable measures. Since it is less sensitive to extreme values, MAE is our preferred option (Hair et al., 2022). In addition, out-of-sample predictive capacity was also assessed by means of the cross-validated predictive ability test (CVPAT) procedure (Lienggaard et al., 2021) comparing whether the average loss of the PLS-SEM model is significantly lower than the average loss value of a prediction using indicator averages (IA) and the average loss value of a linear model (LM).

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